

THE ROLE OF SiC REINFORCEMENT ON HIGH TEMPERATURE CREEP OF SiC/2124AL METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The role of SiC whiskers and particles on creep deformation of SiC/2124Al composites were investigated by the constant stress creep tests at 300°C. The creep resistance of SiC/2124Al composites were sensitively dependent on the effective stress acting on the 2124Al matrix. A new concept of effective aspect ratio was proposed combining the effects of both the aspect ratio and the alignment of whiskers. The steady state creep rates and sub-grain sizes were measured similar under the identical effective stress on 2124Al matrix. It is suggested that the creep deformation of composite proceed by the deformation of matrix and the role of SiC reinforcement is to reduce the effective stress acting on matrix through the load transfer from matrix to reinforcement. A modified power law creep equation was proposed to describe the creep behavior of SiC/2124Al composites.

INTRODUCTION

Discontinuous metal matrix composites(MMCs) have improved modulus and strength at room and elevated temperature due to the presence of ceramic reinforcements[1,2]. The conventional deformation processing techniques, such as forging, rolling and extrusion, can be applicable to the discontinuous MMCs to make complicated shaped parts[1-4]. As the fabrication cost of MMCs containing discontinuous reinforcement is lowered, the MMCs become more attractive as the high performance structural materials. In recent years, with growing interests of MMCs for high temperature applications, the high temperature mechanical behavior of discontinuous silicon carbide reinforced aluminum matrix composites have been investigated by several researchers[4-11]. From the results of previous investigations, the general feature on creep deformation of discontinuous SiC reinforced Al matrix composites can be summarized as follows. The creep resistance of composites is improved than those of matrix Al alloys. The stress exponents for creep deformation of composites ranged 7-20 are much higher than those of matrix Al alloys

ranged 3-5. The activation energies for creep deformation of composites are higher than those for self diffusion of matrix Al alloys, even though the creep is proceeded by the deformation of matrix. These general phenomena on the creep behavior of SiC/Al composites have been widely investigated, however the role of SiC reinforcement on creep behavior has not been clearly understood yet.

In this study, the high temperature creep behavior of 20 vol% SiC/2124Al composites reinforced with SiC particles and whiskers having different microstructural parameters has been investigated. The effects of aspect ratio and alignment of SiC reinforcement on creep behavior of SiC/2124Al composites were discussed and analyzed quantitatively. The role of SiC reinforcement on high temperature creep deformation of SiC/2124Al composites has been discussed, and a modified creep equation is proposed based on the concept of the load transfer between matrix and reinforcement.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The 20vol.% SiC_w/2124Al and SiC_p/2124Al composites were fabricated by powder metallurgy process. The α -SiC particles with average size of 8 μ m, and β -SiC whiskers with average diameter of 1.5 μ m and length of 50-60 μ m were used as reinforcements. The atomized 2124Al powders with average diameter of 20 μ m were used as matrix. The SiC reinforcements and 2124Al powders were wet mixed in ethanol of pH9 with stirring for 1hr. The mixtures were dried at 70°C for 12hrs and were consolidated by vacuum hot pressing at 570°C with a pressure of 90MPa under 1×10^{-5} Torr. The consolidated ingots were hot extruded at 500°C with different extrusion ratios of 10:1, 15:1 and 25:1, and the extruded bars were solution heat treated at 493°C for 2hrs followed by aging at 192°C for 8hrs.

Constant stress creep tests were conducted using a constant stress cam under applied stress ranged 70-110MPa at 300°C. The temperature variation of specimen was maintained within $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ during the creep test. The dimensional change of specimen during creep deformation was measured using a linear variable differential transformer(LVDT) with a resolution of $\pm 0.005\text{mm}$. The aspect ratios of whiskers were measured and the alignments of whiskers were observed by scanning electron microscope(SEM). The degrees of SiC whisker alignment from the extrusion axis were analyzed quantitatively by X-ray pole figures constructed from (111) diffraction peak of SiC whiskers. The sub-grain sizes in 2124Al matrix of composites were observed and measured from TEM micrographs. The thin foils for TEM observation were mechanically polished to a thickness of about 100 μ m and were dimpled to a thickness of about 20 μ m, then followed by the ion milling.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The variation of steady state creep rates of SiC/2124Al composites, with varying applied stress is shown in Fig. 1. The SiC_w/2124Al composites showed much higher creep resistance compared to the SiC_p/2124Al composites. The SiC_w/2124Al composites extruded with 15:1 showed the lowest steady state creep rate indicating the highest creep resistance. The steady state creep rates of SiC/2124Al composites followed the power law creep behavior as fitted into straight lines in Fig.1. The stress exponents were measured about 9, and the activation energies were measured as 340-395kJ/mol for creep deformation of SiC/2124Al composites.

During the creep of metal matrix composites with ceramic reinforcements, it is suggested that the deformation takes place in creeping matrix and the non-creeping ceramic reinforcement improve the creep resistance by reducing the effective stress on matrix by sharing a part of applied stress.

Fig. 1 The variation of steady state creep rates of SiCp/2124Al and SiCw/2124Al composites with varying applied stress at 300°C

In order to analyze the role of SiC reinforcement on creep resistance of composites, the transfer of applied stress between matrix and reinforcement during creep deformation was investigated. The effective stress on matrix in discontinuous reinforced MMCs can be calculated based on the modified shear lag model using the load transfer equation proposed by Nardone et al.[15] as following Eqn.(1).

$$\sigma = V_f \cdot (\tau_i \cdot S + \sigma_i) + V_m \cdot \sigma_i \quad (1)$$

where σ is applied stress, σ_i is average stress in composites, τ_i is shear stress transferred from matrix to reinforcement, S is aspect ratio of reinforcement and V_f , V_m are the volume fractions of reinforcement and matrix, respectively. The second term of right side of Eqn.(1) indicates the effective stress shared by the matrix, which contributes to the creep deformation of composite. The ratio of effective stress to applied stress can be expressed as Eqn.(2) by assuming that the τ_i is equal to $\sigma_i/2$ [16].

$$\frac{\sigma_{eff}}{\sigma} = \frac{\sigma - \sigma_r}{\sigma} = 1 - \frac{V_f \cdot (S/2 + 1)}{V_f \cdot (S/2 + 1) + V_m} \quad (2)$$

where σ_{eff} is effective stress on matrix, σ is applied stress and σ_r is stress shared by reinforcements. As the volume fraction of reinforcement, V_f , is 0.2, the aspect ratio of SiC particles is 1 and the average aspect ratio of SiC whiskers were measured as 4.1 from SEM micrographs, the fraction of effective stress on the matrix, σ_{eff}/σ , is calculated as 0.73 for SiCp/2124Al and 0.56 for SiCw/2124Al composites from Eqn.(2). This means that the effective stress on the matrix is 73% of applied stress in SiCp/2124Al and 56% of applied stress in SiCw/2124Al composites.

The modified shear lag model is based on the assumption that all the reinforcements are aligned parallel to the loading axis in matrix. However, if the alignment of reinforcements is not perfectly parallel, the alignment of reinforcements needs to be considered as another factor influencing the effective stress[17]. The SiC whiskers are distributed quite randomly in SiCw/2124Al composites after consolidated by vacuum hot pressing. The SiC whiskers are aligning more parallel to the extrusion axis, at the same time, the whiskers are broken due to the damage during the hot extrusion process. The different aspect ratio and alignment of SiC reinforcement could be attained by varying the extrusion ratio, and the effects of these two microstructural parameters on creep behavior were analyzed. Fig.2 shows that the aspect ratio of SiC whiskers decreased with increasing extrusion ratio, since the average length of SiC whiskers decreased due to the damage

of whiskers during the hot extrusion process. At the same time, the alignment of whiskers became more parallel to the extrusion axis with increasing extrusion ratio in Fig.2.

Fig.2 SEM micrograph of SiCw/2124Al composites showing the alignment and aspect ratio of SiC whiskers. (a) Extrusion ratio of 10:1, (b) extrusion ratio of 15:1, (c) extrusion ratio of 25:1.

Since the β -SiC whiskers are single crystals grown along $\langle 111 \rangle$ direction, the relative X-ray diffraction intensity from (111) plane of whiskers in X-ray pole figure obtained from the cross-sectional surface perpendicular to the extrusion axis of SiCw/2124Al, shown in Fig.3, is proportional to the density of whiskers aligned with misorientation angle, θ , from the extrusion axis. The steeper reduction of X-ray diffraction intensity from (111) plane with increasing extrusion ratio in Fig.3 indicates the improved alignment of SiC whiskers at higher extrusion ratio. The density function of whiskers, $F(\theta)$, is proposed as Eqn.(3) for quantitative analysis of whisker alignment, since the (111) peak intensity from SiC whiskers decreased exponentially with increasing misorientation angle, θ .

$$F(\theta) = \alpha \cdot \exp(-K \cdot \theta) \quad (3)$$

where θ is misorientation angle from the extrusion axis, α and K are constants. Assuming that the load transfer efficiency of a whisker having aspect ratio S and aligned with angle θ from the extrusion axis is proportional to the $S \cos^2 \theta$, an effective aspect ratio, S_{eff} , can be formulated as Eqn.(4) considering all whiskers in the composites by integrating for the whole hemisphere shown in Fig.4[17].

$$\begin{aligned} S_{\text{eff}} &= \int_0^{\pi/2} (S \cdot \cos^2 \theta) F(\theta) 2\pi \sin \theta d\theta \\ &= \pi \alpha \left\{ \frac{1 - K \exp(-K\pi/2)}{2(1 + K^2)} + \frac{3 + K \exp(-K\pi/2)}{2(9 + K^2)} \right\} \cdot S \\ &= C_0 \cdot S \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{let, } C_0 = \pi \alpha \left\{ \frac{1 - K \exp(-K\pi/2)}{2(1 + K^2)} + \frac{3 + K \exp(-K\pi/2)}{2(9 + K^2)} \right\} \quad (5)$$

where S is average aspect ratio of whiskers and C_0 is alignment compensation factor related with the degree of the whisker alignment. Considering the load transfer efficiency of the imperfectly aligned whiskers, the equation to calculate the effective stress on matrix needs to be modified by substituting S_{eff} for S in Eqn.(2) as following;

$$\frac{\sigma_{eff}}{\sigma} = 1 - \frac{V_f \cdot (S_{eff} / 2 + 1)}{V_f \cdot (S_{eff} / 2 + 1) + V_m} \quad (6)$$

where σ is applied stress, V_f and V_m are volume fractions of reinforcement and matrix, respectively, and S_{eff} is effective aspect ratio of reinforcement.

Fig. 3 The variation of diffracted X-ray intensity from extruded SiCw/2124Al composites with extrusion ratio of 10:1, 15:1 and 25:1 with varying misorientation angle.

Fig. 4 A schematic diagram of the three dimensional geometry of SiC whisker alignment showing the division of integration area.

The variations of the average aspect ratio, alignment compensation factor and effective aspect ratio of whiskers with varying the extrusion ratio are shown in Fig.5. The alignment compensation factor increased with increasing extrusion ratio from 10:1 to 25:1, which indicates the improvement of whisker alignment with increasing the extrusion ratio. The average aspect ratio decreased with increasing the extrusion ratio due to the increased damage of whiskers at higher extrusion ratio. However, the effective aspect ratio of whiskers, which is a multiplication of average aspect ratio with alignment compensation factor was the largest in composite extruded with 15:1. Comparing the creep resistance of SiC/2124Al composites with different extrusion ratio, the creep resistance was found to be increased with increasing the effective aspect ratio of whiskers. By using the effective aspect ratio, S_{eff} , instead of the average aspect ratio, S , the effective stresses can be calculated from Eqn.(6) for SiC_w/2124Al composites extruded with 10:1, 15:1 and 25:1, respectively. Fig. 6 shows the variation of the steady state creep rates with varying the calculated effective stress, which is replotted using the creep data in Fig. 1.

Fig. 5 The variation of alignment compensation factor, average and effective aspect ratio of whiskers in SiCw/2124Al composites with varying extrusion ratio.

Fig. 6 The variation of steady state creep rates of SiC/2124Al composites with varying effective stress at 300°C

The steady state creep rates of SiC_p/2124Al and SiC_w/2124Al composites extruded with different ratios were found to be almost similar under identical effective stress. These results strongly indicate that the role of SiC reinforcement during creep of SiC/2124Al composites is to reduce the effective stress for creep deformation of matrix through the load transfer from matrix to reinforcements.

Fig.7 shows a stable sub-grain structure developed in 2124Al matrix of SiC/2124Al composite during the creep deformation at 300°C. The steady state creep rate was sensitively dependent on the sub-grain size in 2124Al matrix as shown in Fig.8. Fig.9(a) shows that the sub-grain sizes in SiC_w/2124Al and SiC_p/2124Al were measured quite different at the identical applied stress. However, Fig.9(b) shows that the sub-grain sizes in SiC_w/2124Al and SiC_p/2124Al composites were measured similar at the identical effective stress on matrix. This indicates that the sub-grain size of matrix, which is related to the steady state creep rates of composites, is dependent on the effective stress, not on the applied stress. This observation on the direct relationship between effective stress and sub-grain size strongly suggests that the role of SiC reinforcements during high temperature creep of SiC/2124Al composite is to reduce the effective stress for creep deformation of matrix through the load transfer from matrix to reinforcement.

Fig. 7 The TEM micrograph showing the sub-grain structure developed in SiC_p/2124Al composite during creep deformation under the applied stress of 92MPa at 300°C.

Fig. 8 The variation of steady state creep rate of SiC/2124Al composites with varying sub-grain size at 300°C.

Fig. 9 The variation of sub-grain size of 2124Al matrix of composites with varying stress during creep deformation at 300°C. (a) Plotted with applied stress, (b) Plotted with effective stress.

The creep behavior of metals or alloys is generally expressed by the power law creep equation[18] as following:

$$\frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{D} = A \frac{Gb}{kT} \left(\frac{\sigma}{G} \right)^n \quad (7)$$

where $\dot{\epsilon}$ is steady state creep rate, D is diffusion coefficient, G is shear modulus, b is length of Burgers vector, k is Boltzmann's constant, T is temperature, σ is applied stress and A is constant. As the creep behavior of composite is directly related to the effective stress considering the load transfer efficiency of reinforcements, the applied stress, σ , in Eqn.(7), σ , needs to be replaced with the effective stress, σ_{eff} , for composites expressed as Eqn.(8):

$$\frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{D} = A \frac{Gb}{kT} \left(\frac{\sigma_{eff}}{G} \right)^n \quad (8)$$

where σ_{eff} is effective stress shared by the matrix, which is dependent on the applied stress, volume fraction, and effective aspect ratio of reinforcement. By introducing the Eqn.(6) for the effective stress, the power law creep equation is modified as :

$$\frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{D} = A \frac{Gb}{kT} \left[\left\{ 1 - \frac{V_f(S_{eff} / 2 + 1)}{V_f(S_{eff} / 2 + 1) + V_m} \right\} \cdot \frac{\sigma}{G} \right]^n \quad (9)$$

The Fig. 10 shows that the relationship between normalized effective stress and normalized steady state creep rate of composites having different microstructural parameters of reinforcements plotted using the Eqn.(9). The stress exponent for creep deformation was measured about 9 and is similar the values measured by the other investigators[7-11].

Fig. 10 The variation of normalized steady state creep rates of SiC/2124Al composites with varying normalized effective stress at 300°C

The constant A of Eqn.(9) was calculated to be 6.8×10^{11} using the physical data of Al obtained as, 20.8GPa for G[11], 0.286nm for b[22], and $1.56 \times 10^{-17} \text{m}^2/\text{s}$ for D at 300°C. Then, a modified power law creep equation to describe the creep behavior of SiC/2124Al composite is proposed as following Eqn.(10).

$$\frac{\dot{\epsilon}}{D} = 6.8 \times 10^{11} \frac{Gb}{kT} \left[\left\{ 1 - \frac{V_f(S_{eff} / 2 + 1)}{V_f(S_{eff} / 2 + 1) + V_m} \right\} \cdot \frac{\sigma}{G} \right]^9 \quad (10)$$

The steady state creep rates of composites with various microstructural parameters of reinforcements can be predicted by the above proposed modified power law creep equation.

CONCLUSIONS

The creep resistances of SiC/2124Al composites were sensitively dependent on the effective stress acting on the matrix. An effective aspect ratio was proposed combining the effects of the aspect ratio and alignment of whiskers on the load transfer from matrix to reinforcement. The effective stresses for creep deformation of 2124Al matrix were formulated using the effective aspect ratios of SiC whiskers. The steady state creep rates of SiC/2124Al composites with different aspect ratio and alignment of SiC reinforcements were found to be similar under the identical effective stress on 2124Al matrix. Furthermore, the sub-grain sizes in 2124Al matrix were measured similar under the identical effective stress on 2124Al matrix. These results indicate that the creep deformation proceed in the 2124Al matrix of composite and the role of SiC reinforcements is to reduce the effective stress on matrix through the load transfer from matrix to reinforcements. A modified power law creep equation was proposed to describe the creep behavior of SiC/2124Al composites.

REFERENCES

- [1] K. K. Chawla, Composite Materials, New York, Springer-Verlag (1987), pp.4-10
- [2] R. K. Everett and R. J. Arsenault, Metal Matrix Composites, New York: Academic Press (1991), p.97
- [3] R. J. Arsenault, Metal Matrix Composite, New York, Addison-Wesley (1990), p.110
- [4] D. Webster, Met. Trans., **13A**,1511 (1992)
- [5] V. C. Nardone and J. R. Strife, Met. Trans., **18A**, 109 (1987)
- [6] G. Egglar, Z. Metallkd., **85**, 1 (1994)
- [7] G. Gonzalez and O. D. Sherby, Acta Metall. Mater., **41**, 2797 (1993)
- [8] T. L. Dragone and W. D. Nix, Acta Metall. Mater., **40**, 2781 (1992)
- [9] V. C. Nardone and J. K. Tien., Scr. Metall. Mater., **20**, 797 (1987)
- [10] A. B. Pandy, R. S. Mishra and Y. R. Mehajan, Scr. Metall., **24**, 5651 (1990)
- [11] K. T. Park, E. J. Lavernia and F. A. Mohamed, Acta Metall. Mater., **38**, 2149 (1990)
- [12] T. L. Dragone and W. D. Nix, Acta Metall. Mater., **38**, 1941 (1990)
- [13] A. F. Whitehouse and T. W. Clyne, Acta Metall. Mater., **41**, 1701 (1993)
- [14] S. H. Hong and K. H. Chung, Proc. of JIMIS-7, Sendai, Japan (1993), p.263
- [15] V. C. Nardone and K. M. Prewo, Scr. Metall. Mater., **20**, 43 (1986)
- [16] M. R. Piggot, Load Bearing Fiber Composites, Oxford, Pergamon Press (1980)
- [17] S. H. Hong and K. H. Chung, Mater. Sci. Eng. A, in press (1994)
- [18] J. Cadek, " Creep in Metallic Materials", Elsevier, Oxford, (1988) p. 52
- [19] A. B. Pandy, R. S. Mishra and Y. R. Mahajan, Acta Metall. Mater., **40**, 245 (1992)
- [20] S. Takeuchi and A. S. Argon, J. Mater. Sci., **11**, 1542 (1976)
- [21] T. J. Ginter and F. A. Mohamed, J. Mater. Sci., **17**, 2007 (1982)
- [22] O. D. Sherby, R. H. Klundt and K. Miller, Met. Trans. A, **8A**, 843(1977)
- [23] T. G. Nieh, K. Xia and T. G. Langdon, J. of Eng. Mater. Tech., **110**, 77 (1988)